

SHORT NOTES

Addition Complexes of Sulphur Trioxide with Fatty Acids

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In continuation of our work on sulphur trioxide complexes of ethers¹ and esters², a study of conductance of mixtures of sulphur trioxide and fatty acids has been undertaken. Formation of complexes of acetic acid, propionic acid, butyric acid, and isovaleric acid with sulphur trioxide has been studied. The fatty acids have a low conductance in pure state. On addition of sulphur trioxide to these acids, there is an increase in their conductance. This increase in conductance continues till a maximum is reached which occurs at sulphur trioxide/acid molar ratio between 0.2 and 0.3.

After reaching the maximum the conductance begins to fall with increase of SO₃ contents. In all the acids, except isovaleric, the formation of complexes is indicated by a break in the downward trend of the curves at SO₃/acid molar ratio of 1:2. In isovaleric acid, the break in the curve is indicated by a maximum at the same ratio. Further addition of SO₃ causes the mixtures to become very viscous. The conductance-composition curves are shown in Fig. 1.

The chances for SO₃ to dehydrate acetic acid to acetic anhydride are remote, as the temperature at which addition is made is near the freezing point of the acid. A mixture of calculated quantities of acetic anhydride, sulphuric acid, and acetic acid was put to conductivity measurements. The resistance found was comparatively quite high. This is in accord with the observation of Hall and Voge³ for the system acetic anhydride—sulphur trioxide—water.

Since SO₃ is a strong Lewis acid with *sp*² electronic configuration, it may combine with the acid through an oxygen as lone pairs of electrons are available. The transformation of triangular planar (*sp*²) configuration to tetrahedral (*sp*³) may be due to the new linkage coming into effect. The complex compound so formed may further ionise into two ionic species to help in electrical conduction.

1. Paul and Narula, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 184.

2. Paul, Narula, and Meyer, N. I. S. I. Symposium 'Electrochemistry'.

3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 239.

FIG. 1. SO_3 with various acids.

1. Acetic at 26° . 2. Propionic at 28° . 3. Butyric at 27° . 4. Isovaleric at 25° .

In general, the reaction may be represented as:

(where C and D are new ionic species).

Greenwood *et al.*⁴ have proposed the ionisation of the complex of a fatty acid with boron trifluoride as:

The course of formation of new ions may be the same in the present case also. More physical studies bearing on the subject are in hand and will be published soon.